

THE DECAY OF HYDROGEN OVERPOTENTIAL AT MERCURY SURFACE.

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The decay of hydrogen overpotential was noted against coloured electrode during the electrolytic reduction of maleic and fumaric acids in an aerobic condition. A tentative scheme as to the various stages that might occur during the discharge of H ion has been suggested and discussed.

It is well known that a certain amount of overvoltage is necessary to liberate hydrogen at a cathode. Different opinions are held regarding the nature and mechanism of overvoltage as is evident from the good review made by Writz (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1938, **44**, 303). A knowledge of the rate of decay of overvoltage after switching off the polarising current is obviously necessary to gain a proper insight into the nature of the phenomenon. Little work, however, seems to have been done in this direction, the only important data available being those of Bowden and Rideal (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, **A**, **120**, 59), who give the rate to be

$$dE_s/dt = k_1 e^{-k_2 E_s}$$

where E_s is the overvoltage, and of Baars (*Ber. Ges. Ford. Naturwiss. Marburg*, 1928, **63**, 213), according to whom the rate of decay is

$$dE_s/dt = -b/t,$$

where "b" is Tafel's constant.

Ghosh and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **9**, 43; *Biochem. Z.*, 1935, **279**, 296) and Ganguli (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 656) recorded the decay of hydrogen overpotential after reducing the oxidant electrolytically at a mercury cathode. In their several experiments the E.M.F. of the cell, Hg-H₂/Redox System/0.1N-calomel electrode was actually observed to increase after switching off the reducing current {cf. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **9**, 43, Fig. 2, p. 750(2)}.

During the electrolytic reduction of maleic and fumaric acids at Hg electrode in an aerobic condition with the decay of hydrogen overpotential noted against N/10-calomel electrode, no definite potential corresponding to a redox system could be obtained, but the E.M.F. of the cell was found to gradually decay to indefinite values corresponding more or less to the

p_H value of the solution. In several cases the E.M.F. was found actually to increase to a maximum after switching off the current and then decay to indefinite values. In absence of any reducible substance, however, the E.M.F. without showing any increase always decays down to indefinite values from the moment the current is switched off.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The main experimental procedure was similar to that described by Ghosh, Raichaudhuri, and Ganguli (*loc. cit.*). The solution after proper de-aeration was cathodically polarised for requisite duration at a Hg cathode, the polarising current was then cut off and the variation of potential with time was noted.

Scrupulous care was taken to avoid the presence of the slightest trace of extraneous organic matter and oxygen. The ordinary laboratory distilled water was redistilled three times (i) from acid permanganate, (ii) from alkaline permanganate, (iii) from a Jena glass still before use. Sodium sulphate used was strongly ignited in a platinum-crucible. Maleic acid and fumaric acid were recrystallised several times from triple distilled water. The greatest difficulty was experienced in obtaining a supply of nitrogen free from organic matters and oxygen as well. Chemically pure nitrogen, prepared from a mixture of ammonium sulphate, sodium nitrite and potassium chromate, was purified by passing through a heated tube containing CuO. It was then passed through a lime tower in which freshly ignited lime was used. The gas was next passed through a heated tube containing palladinised copper in order to free it from the last traces of oxygen, the original Cu/ammonia method having been found unsuitable. The gas was then passed through a saturator and finally into the solution. All glass to glass joints were ground but not greased. They were protected by mercury seals. It is true that lubricators like "Apiezohn" or "Airtite" which are used for high vacuum work have very low vapour pressure, but even they could not be used. Probably, either the solution was spoilt by mechanical contamination or the small amounts of grease that were carried by the nitrogen, which had to be passed for a long time for deaeration, was sufficient to spoil the experiment.

The electrolysing vessel had also to be modified. A Göckel type mercury sealed stop-cock with wide bore (4-5 mm.) was used to join the anode and cathode chambers (Fig. 1). A small platinum wire B was sealed into the anode chamber to serve as an auxiliary cathode. During electrolysis it was connected through a very high resistance to the negative pole

FIG. 1.

of the supplying source so that a small negative potential was maintained at this electrode and the diffusion of oxygen from the anode chamber to the cathode chamber was effectively prevented. Both the anode and cathode chambers were tall, so that contact with the rubber stopper could be prevented. It was also essential to start with a dry vessel before beginning the experiment.

The cathode chamber had the usual arrangement. The reference electrode was $N/10$ -calomel electrode connected with the solution by a saturated KCl bridge with a mercury-sealed stop-cock and a mercury-sealed ground glass joint. As this does not totally prevent diffusion of oxygen a small current of N_2 was maintained throughout. Every day the apparatus was kept filled up with alkaline permanganate solution after use and before use it was washed with a solution of pure hydrogen peroxide (prepared in the laboratory from pure Na_2O_2 and H_2SO_4 , G.R.), hot caustic soda solution and nitric acid and was finally dried in steam.

"Cenco" pure rubber stoppers were used in both the chambers after prolonged boiling in water. Merck's G. R. mercury distilled at a low

pressure was used. A Töpler pump was used for generating low pressure in preference to oil pump in order to avoid last traces of grease from mercury.

The electrolysing current was obtained from a 110 volt D.C. supply by means of potentiometer arrangement. Potential measurements were made with an ordinary hydrogen ion potentiometer. But when readings had to be taken at very small intervals this was found unsuitable. So a balanced triode circuit was designed. Two Phillip's HL_2 valves were used in opposition. It was found that if after keeping the anode voltage 150 and the filament current 0.2 amps a negative potential of -2.5 volts was applied to the grids, the current in the grid circuit became negligible (less than 10^{-9} amps). The galvanometer deflections were calibrated by impressing known potentials from a potentiometer at X. The usual precautions regarding shielding were observed.

FIG. 2.

A solution containing 10^{-5} M-fumaric acid in $N/10$ -sodium sulphate was reduced cathodically for different lengths of time. Fig. 2 gives the variation of E.M.F. with time. Curve I was obtained after electrolysis for 90 seconds, curves II and III for 30 and 20 seconds respectively. Results of similar observations with a solution containing $10M$ -fumaric acid in $N/10$ -sodium sulphate are shown in Fig. 3. Curve I was obtained after electrolysis for 510 seconds, curve II for 150 seconds and curve III for 54 seconds. In all

cases a current density of 3.33×10^{-4} amps/sq. cm. was used. Below are given two typical data with different concentrations of fumaric acid in $N/10$ -sodium sulphate electrolysed for different lengths of time.

TABLE I.

$10^{-1}M$ -Fumaric acid electrolysed for 20 sec.				$10^{-2}M$ -Fumaric acid electrolysed for 140 sec.			
Time.*	E.M.F.	Time.	E.M.F.	Time.*	E.M.F.	Time.	E.M.F.
0 sec.	240 sec.	-1.369 volt.	0 sec.	-1.325 volt.	180 sec.	-1.451 volt.
30	-1.320 volt.	420	-1.300	30	-1.372	360	-1.279
60	-1.370	480	-1.241	60	-1.442	840	-1.012
90	-1.402	1050	-0.956	90	-1.472	1740	-0.831
120	-1.425	1800	-0.821	120	-1.498	21300	-0.7725
150	-1.420			150	-1.470		

* (After the current was switched off).

* (After switching off the current).

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

Table I shows that when the time for electrolysis is too small (below 54 seconds for 10^{-2} - M fumaric acid) the E.M.F. of the cell decays exponentially after the current is switched off. Only when the time for electrolysis is between definite limits, the E.M.F. of the cell at first rises after switching off the current and then falls.

Effect of Concentration of Reducible Substances.

Fumaric acid of different concentrations was electrolysed for 60 seconds with a current density of 3.33×10^{-4} amp./sq. cm and the rate of variation of E.M.F. was noted after the reducing current was stopped and the results of such experiments graphically represented in Fig. 4.

Curves I-VI represent respectively $10^{-3}M$, $10^{-4}M$, $M/500$, $M/250$ and $M/100$ -fumaric acid solutions in $N/10$ - Na_2SO_4 .

From the above figures it will be observed that whenever the E.M.F. of the cell immediately after switching off the current is greater than about 1.50 volts or less than about 1.35 volts, the E.M.F. of the cell decays exponentially with time after the current is switched off. But if the E.M.F. is between these two limits, it at first rises after switching off the current and then decays.

If any reducing substance be not present, the E.M.F. of the cell rises rapidly during electrolysis and when the current is stopped it decays exponentially without passing through a maximum. Owing to the experimental difficulties involved, the effect of change of p_{H} value of the solution was not very clear. The effect was however very small, if any at all.

D I S C U S S I O N.

During electrolysis the processes that may take place at the cathode are (i) discharge of hydrogen ions, (ii) reduction of the reducible substances present, and (iii) discharge of sodium ions.

Heyrasymenko (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1935, **44**, 303) found that the deposition of Na on a Hg electrode does not start until the cathode is about 2 volts negative to the $N/10$ -calomel electrode. Since the rise and fall of E.M.F. is observed when the E.M.F. of the cell is 1.30 to 1.50 volts, it is obvious that under experimental conditions no Na^+ was discharged on the mercury electrode. Only the processes nos. (i) and (ii) as mentioned above occurred in this case.

The following stages may be supposed to occur during the discharge of hydrogen ions: (i) movement of the ions upto the electrode, (ii) neutralisation by the transfer of an electron from the cathode to the ion, (iii) dehydration, (iv) adsorption of the hydrogen atom produced on the cathode

surface, (v) combination of the atoms produced to form H_2 molecules, and (vi) evaporation of the hydrogen molecules so formed.

The above represents only a tentative scheme. All of them may not take place in the order given and some of them may be simultaneous. According to Tafel (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, **50**, 641) hydrogen overvoltage is due to the slow speed of the reaction taking place in stage (v). On the other hand Volmer, Erdey Gruz and their collaborators (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **A**, **150**, 203; 1932, **162**, 53) and many others think that the bottle neck is at stage (ii), and is the cause of hydrogen overvoltage. In our discussions we shall assume that neither of the stages are instantaneous and both have comparable velocities.

Since the hydrogen ions move faster than sodium ions, most of the positive current in the solution is carried by the hydrogen ions to the cathode. The main bulk of the solution thus becomes comparatively poor in hydrogen ions whereas the region near the cathode-electrolyte interface receives a large amount of these ions. Owing to the slow speed of transference of electrons from the electrodes to the ions, all of them are not immediately neutralised. There is thus an excess of hydrogen ions near the cathode-electrolyte interface. When the polarising current is stopped, this excess of hydrogen ions diffuses towards the bulk of the solution, thus causing a rise in the E.M.F. after switching off the current. On the other hand, the hydrogen atoms that accumulated on the electrode during electrolysis will combine to form H_2 molecules and evaporate as such for some time after the current is switched off. The E.M.F. of the cell will tend to fall owing to this. Owing to these two opposing tendencies the E.M.F. may at first rise and then fall.

The rate of diffusion of hydrogen ions from the immediate neighbourhood of the cathode-electrolyte interface to the bulk of the solution will depend on the concentration gradient of the hydrogen ions. According to Bowden (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 473) when the E.M.F. is above 1.60 volts, the interface is comparatively depleted of hydrogen ions by discharge. Hence above 1.60 volts diffusion of hydrogen ions towards the interior will be slow and the rate of increase in E.M.F. due to diffusion will also be small. Again if the surface concentration of H atoms on the cathode reaches very high values, the reaction $2H = H_2$ becomes rapid and the rate of fall in E.M.F. owing to this reaction may under this condition exceed the rate of rise in E.M.F., so that the E.M.F. of the cell will begin to decay exponentially immediately after the current is switched off.

We can now distinguish two sets of circumstance :

(i) *When no reducible substances are present.* Under these circumstances all the hydrogen atoms that are discharged accumulate on the electrode and the concentration of H atoms rapidly reaches high values. This is what happens when no reducible substances are present and a solution of pure sodium sulphate is electrolysed. The E.M.F. of the cell becomes high very rapidly (more than 1.60 volts) and then decays exponentially after the current is switched off. If some reducible substances are present, a part of the hydrogen is consumed by them and a low hydrogen atom concentration on the electrode is maintained for a longer period.

(ii) *If prolonged electrolysis is carried out.* Under this circumstances (when the voltage is above 1.60) the interface region becomes comparatively depleted of hydrogen ions whereas a large amount of hydrogen ions accumulate on the electrode. Rate of fall of E.M.F. now exceeds the rate of rise. So we obtain an exponential fall in the E.M.F. from the very beginning. Again when the time for electrolysis is very small, the hydrogen ions in the immediate neighbourhood of the electrode are discharged, but a sufficient number do not arrive from the interior to establish an appreciable concentration gradient. Hence in this case also we shall not obtain any rise of E.M.F.

It is to be noted in this connection that we cannot obtain this phenomenon when electromotively active normal redox systems such as methylene blue system or ferrous-ferric system are electrolysed since they rapidly establish stable potentials characteristic to themselves. It is only when some electromotively inactive system such as maleic acid or systems whose electrode reactions are slow such as cystine are reduced cathodically, that we may expect to observe such rise and fall of E.M.F.

Hammet (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 770) was the first to suggest that both the electrode processes, $\text{H}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n^+ + e = \text{H} + n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $2\text{H} = \text{H}_2$ are slow and of comparable velocities. Loschkarev and Cossin (*Acta Physicochimica*, 1938, 8, 189) have further extended this idea. The observations made in the foregoing experiments appear to agree with this view so far as mercury surface is concerned.

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